

Behaviour of Salicylic Acid and Sulfo-Salicylic Acid in Concentrated and Dilute Solutions

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Salicylic and sulfo-salicylic acids exhibit the behaviour of a colloidal electrolyte in concentrated solution. They form true solutions at very low concentrations and are useful for spectrophotometric studies of metal chelates. The temperature of zero conductance for salicylic and sulfo-salicylic acids are -29.5° and -20.0° respectively.

Salicylic and sulfo-salicylic acids have been widely used as chelating agents. Das and Aditya¹ have carried out the complex studies using these acids with aluminium by spectrophotometric methods. Verma and Mehrotra² studied the role of concentration in the complexes formed by beryllium with salicylate ions and pointed out the formation of disalicylate ions from the beginning of the reaction. We are contemplating to use these reagents for quantitative estimation. Therefore the behaviour of these acids has been studied at different concentrations.

EXPERIMENTAL

The measurements of electrical conductance were carried out with a Toshniwal Conductivity bridge operated at 220 V/50 cycles a.c. mains and using a measuring cell of dipping type. All the solutions were freshly prepared in conductivity water using salicylic acid (Rhodia) and sulfo-salicylic acid (E. Merck) and kept immersed in a Townson and Mercers precision thermostat throughout the course of the experiment.

The electrical conductance of a series of solutions of salicylic and sulfo-salicylic acids were measured at different dilutions at 34° and 32° respectively. Graphs were plotted between square root of concentration and equivalent conductance (Figs. 1 and 2).

- VARIATION OF Δ OF SALICYLIC ACID WITH \sqrt{C}
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The specific conductance of salicylic and sulfo-salicylic acids were also measured at six different temperatures. The temperatures of zero conductance has been extrapolated and were found to be -29.5° for salicylic acid and -20° for sulfo-salicylic acid (Figs. 3 and 4).

The temperature coefficients per degree centigrade per hundred of the conductance at 35° are recorded.

DISCUSSION

It is observed from Figs. 1 and 2 that aqueous solutions of salicylic and sulfo-salicylic acids do not form exactly true solutions and it possesses some colloidal characteristics, because the curves are not linear³⁻⁸. Similar behaviour has been recorded by McBain⁹ for colloidal electrolytes. If the solutions of salicylic and sulfo-salicylic acids behave as true electrolyte the curves would have been linear and the Debye-Hückle equation would have been applicable. Further it has been found that the temperature of zero conductance for salicylic and sulfo-salicylic acids are -29.5° and -20° respectively and the temperature coefficient per degree centigrade per hundred of the conductance at 35° for salicylic and sulfo-salicylic acids range between 1.23 to 1.55 and 1.43 to 1.83 respectively. These data establish that the solutions of salicylic and sulfo-salicylic acids behave as colloidal electrolyte in concentrated solutions.

The work of Prakash and coworkers¹⁰ also supports the above views. They described that in general, the temperature of zero conductance of true electrolytes lies at -40° , whereas

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in the case of colloidal systems, this temperature ranges between -15° to -35° . They also found that usually the temperature coefficient per degree centigrade per hundred of the conductance at 35° , in colloidal systems is found to be below 2.0.

It appears from Fig. 1 that there are two maxima in the curve for salicylic acid. This observation supports the formation of di-salicylate ions as reported by Verma and Mehrotra (loc. cit). There are at least two maxima and two minima for sulfo-salicylic acid (Fig. 2). These results also find support from the work of Das and Aditya (loc. cit.), and it seems that four species are involved in it. However we failed to determine these species by freezing point depression data.

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